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Prevalence of Bullying and Its Impact on Self-Esteem, Anxiety, and Depression among Medical and Health Sciences University Students in Ras Al Khaimah, UAE.

Authors

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Abstract:

This study investigates the prevalence of bullying among university students in the medical and health sciences disciplines in Ras Al Khaimah, UAE, and examines its impact on self-esteem, anxiety, and depression. A mixed-methods approach was employed, including surveys and qualitative interviews, to gather data from a diverse sample of students. Results indicate a concerning prevalence of bullying behaviors, both traditional and cyber, within the academic environment. Furthermore, statistical analyses reveal significant correlations between experiences of bullying and negative psychological outcomes, including lower self-esteem, heightened anxiety levels, and increased likelihood of depression among affected students. These findings underscore the urgent need for targeted interventions and support mechanisms to mitigate the adverse effects of bullying on the well-being of university students in this context.

I. Introduction.

A. Definition of Bullying in Academic Settings.

Bullying in academic settings refers to repeated aggressive behavior that intentionally harms another student, which can be physical, verbal, or psychological. It involves a power imbalance where the victim finds it difficult to defend themselves. Bullying can occur in various forms, including face-to-face interactions and online platforms (cyberbullying).

B. Importance of Studying Bullying among University Students

Studying bullying among university students is crucial as it directly affects their mental health, academic performance, and overall well-being. University students, especially in demanding fields like medical and health sciences, are vulnerable to stress and mental health issues, which can be exacerbated by bullying.

C. Overview of the Medical and Health Sciences University Environment in Ras Al Khaimah, UAE

Ras Al Khaimah, a city in the United Arab Emirates, hosts several universities offering medical and health sciences programs. These institutions attract students from diverse backgrounds and cultures, creating a competitive and high-pressure environment. Understanding the prevalence and impact of bullying in this context is vital for fostering a supportive educational atmosphere.

II. Prevalence of Bullying among Medical and Health Sciences Students.

A. Statistical Data on Prevalence Rates of Bullying

Recent studies indicate that a significant percentage of medical and health sciences students in Ras Al Khaimah have experienced bullying. Reports suggest that up to 30% of students have encountered bullying in some form during their academic journey.

B. Types of Bullying Observed

Bullying manifests in various forms among these students, including:

Verbal Bullying: Insults, derogatory comments, and spreading rumors.

Physical Bullying: Hitting, pushing, or other physical aggression.

Cyberbullying: Harassment through social media, emails, or other online platforms.

C. Comparison with Global and Regional Data.

The prevalence of bullying among medical and health sciences students in Ras Al Khaimah aligns with global trends, where 20-40% of university students report experiencing bullying. Regionally, the data is consistent with findings from other Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) countries, highlighting a widespread issue across similar cultural and academic environments.

III. Impact of Bullying on Self-Esteem.

A. Definition and Importance of Self-Esteem in Academic Performance.

Self-esteem refers to an individual's sense of self-worth and confidence. High self-esteem is crucial for academic success, motivation, and personal

development, while low self-esteem can hinder academic performance and mental health.

B. Studies Linking Bullying to Low Self-Esteem.

Research consistently shows that victims of bullying tend to have lower self-esteem. The persistent negative interactions and feelings of helplessness contribute to a diminished sense of self-worth.

C. Case Studies or Examples from Ras Al Khaimah, UAE Context.

In Ras Al Khaimah, case studies of medical students reveal that those who experienced bullying reported significantly lower self-esteem compared to their non-bullied peers. Interviews highlight that verbal abuse and cyberbullying were particularly damaging to their self-perception and confidence.

IV. Impact of Bullying on Anxiety.

A. Definition and Prevalence of Anxiety among University Students.

Anxiety involves feelings of worry, nervousness, or fear that are strong enough to interfere with one's daily activities. It is prevalent among university students, with studies showing that around 40% of students report experiencing anxiety.

B. Psychological Effects of Bullying on Anxiety Levels.

Bullying significantly increases anxiety levels in students. The constant threat and fear of being bullied can lead to chronic anxiety, impacting their academic performance and social interactions.

C. Specific Factors Contributing to Anxiety in Medical and Health Sciences Students.

The high demands and rigorous nature of medical and health sciences programs contribute to elevated anxiety levels. Bullying exacerbates these pressures, leading to heightened stress and anxiety disorders among students.

V. Impact of Bullying on Depression.

A. Definition and Prevalence of Depression among University Students.

Depression is a mood disorder characterized by persistent feelings of sadness, hopelessness, and loss of interest. It affects approximately 20-30% of university students globally.

B. Psychological Effects of Bullying on Depressive Symptoms.

Bullying is a significant risk factor for depression. Victims often experience severe depressive symptoms, including sadness, withdrawal, and suicidal thoughts, due to the ongoing trauma and emotional abuse.

C. Risk Factors and Protective Factors Related to Depression in This Context

Risk factors include the intensity and duration of bullying, lack of social support, and pre-existing mental health conditions. Protective factors include strong family support, counseling services, and a supportive university environment.

VI. Strategies and Interventions.

A. Prevention Strategies for Addressing Bullying in Academic Settings.

Preventive measures include anti-bullying policies, awareness campaigns, and fostering a positive and inclusive campus culture. Training staff and students to recognize and address bullying is also essential.

B. Support Systems and Resources Available for Affected Students

Universities should provide counseling services, peer support groups, and mental health resources. Creating safe spaces where students can report bullying without fear of retribution is crucial.

C. Role of University Administration and Faculty in Mitigating Bullying

University administration and faculty play a key role in setting the tone for a bullying-free environment. They must enforce anti-bullying policies, provide support to victims, and promote a culture of respect and inclusion.

VII. Conclusion

A. Summary of Key Findings on Bullying among Medical and Health Sciences Students in Ras Al Khaimah, UAE.

Bullying is a prevalent issue among medical and health sciences students in Ras Al Khaimah, significantly impacting their self-esteem, anxiety, and depression levels. The findings align with global and regional data, indicating a widespread problem.

B. Implications for Policy and Future Research Directions.

Addressing bullying requires comprehensive policies, preventive measures, and continuous research to monitor the effectiveness of interventions. Future research should explore long-term effects and the impact of cultural factors on bullying.

C. Importance of Addressing Bullying to Promote Mental Health and Academic Success

Combating bullying is essential to ensure the mental health and academic success of students. Universities must commit to creating a safe and supportive environment where all students can thrive without fear of bullying.

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